

HAND GESTURE CHARACTER RECOGNITION USING AI DEEP LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

The interaction between two peers can occur when there is a communication medium between these peers such that both can exchange any idea, information, meaning, news or feeling. This communication medium can either be linguistics or can be gestures. The linguistic communication concerns with statistical or rule-based modeling of Natural Language from a computational point of view, whereas Gesture is moving any part of a body (like head or hand) in order to express any meaning or idea. The aim of this report is to review the different proposals about human gesture recognition systems and their achieved experimental results. This report also includes the procedures followed by the recognition systems to process, extract features, classify and recognize different gestures in the images.

INTRODUCTION.

The computational devices used today, like laptops, smart-phones and tablets have digital cameras integrated in them. These devices have one or more processing units and operating systems and are capable of processing millions of computational operations per second. The technological advancements of using computational resources is growing rapidly and it is now possible to create an interface between human and computational devices to communicate by recognizing gestures. Computers Advanced program like Deep Learning CNN can recognize human gestures and perform tasks accordingly. Valuable information is extracted by recognizing human gestures like facial expressions, hand gestures, head gestures, body posture and voice communications. This interface should require common hardware like integrated webcams on laptops and cameras on smart-phones and tablet computers. However certain parameters must be considered so that precise information may be extracted from non-uniform and complex environments like backgrounds with noise and illumination variations. The basic idea of gesture recognition was initially proposed by Myron W. Krueger as new form of human-computer interaction in the middle of seventies. Since then, a significant research on gesture recognition is being done with swift advancements in the computer hardware and computer vision systems. The key problem of human-computer gesture interaction is to make computers understand human gestures. The techniques for recognizing gestures are divided into two main approaches; data glove based and vision-based approach, wherein former requires the user to wear accessories that are connected with the computer and the later does not require any accessories to wear or connect with human body. Instead vision-based approach requires a camera connected with the computer that can generate image of the view. There are two categories of gesture recognition; macro gesture and micro gestures recognition. Macro gestures are concerned with the movement of part of body relative to the body itself. For example, different positions of a hand associated to the human body is considered as Macro gestures. Micro gestures on the other hand, represents the relative position of the sub-part of a part of body. For example, position of fingers relative to a hand of the body is said to be a micro-gesture.

LITERATURE SURVEY

The primary purpose of Human Gesture Recognition System is to enable the device control to understand human gestures and perform actions according to the instructions received from gestures. There are different techniques proposed for recognizing human gestures. The research paper of “Ashis Pradhan, M.K.Ghose and Mohan Pradhan from CSE Department,

SMIT, Majhitar, East-Sikkim, India Accepted 13 Nov. 2012, Available online 1Dec.2012, Vol.2, No.4 (Dec. 2012)” proposes development of a system that recognizes human hand gestures and classifies them either these gestures represent any denary number from 0 to 9 or else. In this system, a low-resolution web-cam is used to capture hand gestures with the background, process the image to extract the hand and recognize gestures. This system then will classify the gestures correctly. There are generally two phases in this system; preprocessing and classification. Initially, the system is provided training for extracting hand gestures only from the whole image, remove unwanted noise and unwanted regions, convert the image into a binary image by applying threshold and then extract distinguishing significant features to form a feature set for classification. During this training phase, a database is maintained for keeping lists of unique binary patterns. Each binary pattern consists of a number of hand gestures. Each binary pattern represents a specific number between 0 and 9. The algorithm proposed for classification phase of gestures is Support Vector Machine (SVM) which is a machine learning algorithm. During image acquisition, the particular constraint included in the system is that both the training as well as testing images is taken at equidistant level. The color of background as well as object in the background other than hand is assumed to be different from skin color. To remove noise from the image, Medium filter is used. For testing phase, the same steps are followed. The test image after processing is compared with the content of repository created in the training phase. Finally, if there is a match of the input binary pattern with any of the binary patterns from the repository, the index of the matched binary pattern from repository is displayed which is considered as a matched gesture that represents a number between 0 and 9 by the system. The methodology proposed by Hamid A. Jalab, Faculty of Computer Science and Information Technology, University Malaya, 50603 Kuala Lumpur, Malayasia published in the year 2012, in his research paper “Static Hand Gesture Recognition for Human Computer Interaction” for gesture recognition system is based on three primary stages; preprocessing,

feature extraction and classification. The preprocessing stage requires reading the color gesture image, converting into gray-scale and then segmenting the gesture part (i.e. hand gesture) by isolating the foreground from background using absolute difference between gesture part and background. For extracting features from the gestures, a new technique is proposed which is called Wavelet Network. This technique does not use traditional activation function for Artificial Neural Networks (ANN). Instead, it uses special mother wavelet as activation function whose selection depends upon the type of signal. The wavelet network feature extraction algorithm first resizes the gray-scale image to 64x64 pixels to decrease processing time. This algorithm then chooses the initial wavelet parameters. Final wavelet parameters are stored as features of gesture image alongwith final feature vectors. For classification of gestures, Neural Network based classifiers are used as they are found to be the most suitable solution for recognizing images and classifying signs. In the training phase, a dataset of hand-gesture images containing 120 images for training and 60 for testing are taken from a digital camera under natural conditions. These are used to train ANN to classify gesture features. For testing phase, features of gestures are extracted in the same way as in the training phase. Here in this phase, 60 gestures of hand image are input to the proposed system to test with different Gaussian Noise values. P. Jenifer Martina, P. Nagarajan and P. Karthikeyan published their research article about “Hand Gesture Recognition Based Real-time Command System” which was issued on 4th April 2013. In this research article, the proposed system focuses on preprocessing, feature extraction and classification on input hand gesture images. The preprocessing on gesture image is applied in two modules i.e. Segmentation and Morphological Filtering. In the segmentation process, the original image is converted into gray-scale and then into Binary Image using Otsu Algorithm. Binary image is then filtered to remove noise from the image by applying Morphological filtering. Edges are then found by using Canny Edge Detector algorithm. These edges are then used to track contours by applying contour tracking algorithm. Finally, for classification of the resulting

gesture image, Support Vector Machines are used as neural network to classify the image. The whole process is used in the training session for classifying the images correctly. During the testing phase, the same process applies, and neural network classifies the image according to the learning classification of images. A method for recognizing human hand gestures was proposed by Ilan Steinberg et. Al. This method considered pixels of the binary image as a feature. In this method, size of the image is reduced in order to reduce computational classification complexity. Mokhtar M. Hasan et. Al. deduced after observations that the fingertip can be used for recognizing the features. Omlin and Vapnik used color histogram for recognition of user hand gestures. In their proposed method, the entire image was partitioned into smaller blocks and then the corresponding histogram was plotted for classification. Oleg Rummyantsey introduced a very efficient method to recognize gestures by representing the test image and the database images using Eigen values. In this method, hand gestures were accurately classified by using the Euclidean distance of Eigen values. In the year 2003, Wu and Balakrishnan used a touch surface to recognize gestures. A real-time micro hand gesture recognition was presented by Hasanuzzaman et. al. in 2004 by using skin color segmentation and multiple-feature based template technique. During the same year, Kim and Fellner used infrared light and fingertips to recognize gestures and hand movements by applying 3D object manipulation and deformation in their work. Scale space feature detection method was proposed by Fang et. al. for the recognition of hand gestures in 2007. In the year 2010, Lee and Hong introduced a real-time gesture recognition system which was based on using stereo camera to obtain the difference image entropy. A year later, the two researchers Dardas and Petriu a real-time system to track and detect bare hands in a cluttered environment. Their method used hand posture and skin detection contours comparison algorithm after the face subtraction. Hand gestures were then recognized by using Principle Components Analysis (PCA) in real-time environment.

Proposed Methodology

This project is designed to deal with recognition of hand gestures and match them with predefined gesture classes in the database. This design is divided into three parts i.e. preprocessing, feature extraction and classification. All these parts are applied to both the training and the testing images.

Following are the gestures that the system can recognize and classify from 1 to 5 respectively:

Illustration 1: Hand Gestures

This system includes a web-cam that can be built into laptop or any web-cam peripheral which will capture the images of hand gestures from outside world and will input to the hand gesture recognition algorithm. This algorithm processes the hand gestures perceived through web-cam according to the predefined instructions and then classifies it accurately. Initially, the algorithm is provided a set of positive and negative images for training purpose. Once the training session completes, the system will then be able to get images from web-cam, process them accordingly and classify them based on the knowledge it had acquired during the training session.

The processes are carried out as follows:

Illustration 2 General Flow Diagram

Experimental Setup

In this set up, the objective is to detect and recognize human hand gesture in the real time using a regular web-cam. For this purpose, this system first acquires the real-time scene from the web-camera which is then preprocessed; i.e. after image is acquired, it is filtered in order to remove unwanted noise. This filtered image is converted from color image into gray-scale image. To reduce the complexity in the system, it is converted into Binary image by applying some threshold. Now there is need to extract features from the images. So, the next part in this system begins is called Feature extraction. In this part, edges of the images are detected because edges contain important information than flat regions. In order to detect the edges, an edge detecting algorithm is required to be applied. In this project, Canny edge detector is used which also has its built-in function in OpenCV. Contours are extracted from the edges of image. This will give a set of points, so smallest area of convex hull will be found so that cover contours. These areas of convex hull will likely be the points on fingers since these are extremes. This fact is used to detect the number of fingers detected from the scene. For this purpose, further deepest deviation points are also detected so that because the entire arm may also be detected in the scene. The system also requires calculating average of all defects. There will be two minimal points of maxima defects for each finger-tip. These minimal two points of defects and maxima defect point form a triangle. If there are no fingers detected, the system will show no counting numbers. If it detects one finger, it will show 1, for two fingers, the resulting output is 2, for three fingers, output is 3, for four fingers, 4 will appear as output and finally for five fingers, the resulting output is 5.

Experimental Results

Conclusion

This proposed Hand Gesture Recognition System does recognize the hand gestures and classifies it accordingly. This paper also proposes method for preprocessing and classification of images, but this system also focuses on improvement so that hand gestures are recognized quickly and correctly. This system acquires the image in real time through the web-cam and preprocesses it. The preprocessed image is then classified as a number from 1 to 5 or null. The input image may contain noise due to illumination and other effects,

therefore, noise is filtered after converting into gray-scale. For simplification, it is further converted into binary image by applying some threshold. Edges and contours are obtained by applying built-in functions of Canny Edge Detection and contours respectively. Finally, the finger tips are counted as the final finger count value. This system is tested with different hand gestures and it was found that this system classifies and recognized the fingers correctly. It represents the number of fingers with an integer number from one to 5. It also recognizes presence of no finger. This system can further be improved and extended to recognize fingers from 6 to 10.

Reference:

Archana S. Ghotkar and Dr. Gajanan K. Kharate.- **STUDY OF VISION BASED HAND GESTURE RECOGNITION USING INDIAN SIGN LANGUAGE** -international journal on smart sensing and intelligent systems vol. 7, no. 1, march 2014.

Chirag Ahuja, - **Human Hand Gesture Recognition System using Computer Vision.**

Chung-Lin Huang, Sheng-Hung Jeng- **A model-based hand gesture recognition system** Machine Vision and Applications (2001) 12: 243–258 - Accepted: 4 September 2000.

Dhanashree Pannase. To analyze hand gesture recognition for electronic device control: Review Available online at: www.ijarcsms.com - ISSN: 2321-7782

e-ISSN 2455–1392 Volume 2 Issue 5, May 2016 pp. 241 – 245 Scientific Journal Impact Factor: 3.468 <http://www.ijcter.com>.

Eshed Ohn-Bar, - **Hand Gesture Recognition in Real Time for Automotive Interfaces: A Multimodal Vision-Based Approach and Evaluations.** IEEE. vol. 15, no. 6, december 2014.

<https://www.pantechsolutions.net/image-processing-projects/matlab-code-for-license-plate-recognition>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HljB0TMRTeQ>

International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research, Volume 5, Issue 4, April-2014 ISSN 2229-5518.

Jacob Eisenstein, Shahram Ghandeharizadeh, Leana Golubchik, **Device Independence and Extensibility in Gesture Recognition*** Department of Computer Science University of Southern California Los Angeles, CA 90089, USA

Jayshree R.Pansare, **Real Time Static Hand Gesture Recognition System in Complex Background that uses Number system of Indian Sign Language.** ISSN: 2278 – 1323. Volume 2, Issue 3, March 2013.

Kunika s. Barai. **HAND GESTURE RECOGNITION FOR HUMAN COMPUTER INTERACTION**

Le Tran Nguyen, Cong Do Thanh, [**Contour Based Hand Gesture Recognition Using Depth Data**]Vol.29 (SIP 2013), pp.60-65. <http://dx.doi.org/10.14257/astl.2013.29.12>

Manisha chahal, B Anil Kumar, Kavita Sharma. **GESTURE RECOGNITION: PROLOGUE**

Markos Sigalas, **Gesture recognition based on arm tracking for human-robot interaction.**

Narendra V. Jagtap¹ Prof. R. K. Somani² Prof. Pankaj Singh Parihar³ – **Hand Gesture Recognition System for Human-Computer Interaction with Web-Cam** Vol. 1, Issue 9, 2013 | ISSN (online): 2321-0613

Sajjad Ur Rahman*, Zeenat Afroze** , Mohammed Tareq* -**Hand Gesture Recognition Techniques For Human Computer Interaction Using OpenCv-** ISSN 2250-3153 International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications, Volume 4, Issue 12, December 2014.

Simon Ruffieux¹, Denis Lalanne², Elena Mugellini¹ and Omar Abou Khaled¹. **A Survey of Datasets for Human Gesture Recognition.** ¹University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Western Switzerland, Fribourg.

The 2010 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems October 18-22, 2010, Taipei, Taiwan

Website: www.ijetae.com (ISSN 2250-2459 (Online), Volume 4, Special Issue 1, February 2014)

Zhenxiang Huang, Bo Peng, and Juan Wu.**Research and Application of Human-Computer Interaction System Based on Gesture Recognition Technology.** China Agricultural University, Beijing 100083, China